

Star Formation in the Central Molecular Zone

Dennis Lee

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Abstract

The region close to the center of the Milky Way, known as the central molecular zone (CMZ), was the subject of the Submillimeter Array in its Legacy Survey. Data from this survey along with data from the Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey and the Atacama Pathfinder EXperiment are used to investigate the nature of the CMZ. Current observations show that the current star formation rate in the CMZ is approximately one order of magnitude below what is predicted by current models. In this study, the 1.6 Degree Cloud (G1.602+0.018) and the 1.1 Degree Cloud (G0.891-0.048) are investigated. Both clouds are outside the immediate central 100 pc region, but still subject to increased temperatures, densities, and turbulence characteristic of the CMZ. Dense cores have been identified in the 1.6 Degree Cloud suggesting the existence of star formation, despite the turbulent nature of the region. One core is identified in the 1.1 Degree Cloud though the star-forming nature of this core is unclear. Thus, further higher resolution observations of the 1.1 Degree Cloud are recommended. The identification of these dense cores and measurement of their physical properties performed in this study will allow researchers, in combination with similar analyses of other regions, to understand how stars form in the CMZ, and how that compares with more well-understood star formation in the disk of our Galaxy.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Stars are the fundamental units of galaxies and the method by which stars are made and formed is one of the most interesting questions in contemporary astrophysics. Understanding star formation not only presents insight into the origins and formation of planetary systems, but also into the structure and evolution of galaxies.

The current theory of star formation below is summarized from Kennicutt & Evans (2012) and McKee & Ostriker (2007).

1.1 Theory of Star Formation

Star formation in galaxies originates in the gas and dust that exists between the stars in a galaxy. From this dust and gas, known as the interstellar medium (ISM), giant molecular clouds, or GMCs, are created. On the order of $10^5 M_{\odot}$, these GMCs are believed to be condensed out of the ISM as a result of large-scale instabilities (Vogel et al., 1988; Sakamoto et al., 1999; Elmegreen, 1979). These large-scale instabilities include processes such as Parker instabilities and complex Jeans instabilities. In both cases, varying surface densities lead to regions of higher densities to become more and more dense until a self-gravitating GMC is formed. Elmegreen (1994) showed through numerical simulations that these instabilities are more likely to occur in spiral arms suggesting the arms to be likely locations of GMCs, and

thus, star formation.

The largest of these massive structures, giant molecular or atomic superclouds, continue to possess the internal turbulence of the ISM. This turbulence, motions and power that exist at multiple physical scales, creates regions of overdensities and underdensities, and in combination with the structure’s self-gravity, leads the supercloud to fracture and fragment into smaller GMCs of various masses. Within these GMCs, the turbulence continues to exist and leads to a variety of gas densities which subsequently condense into even smaller regions with a variety of masses and sizes. The densest of these regions condense further to create “cores”. These cores are believed to be the precursors to stars or star systems. Originating from these denser regions, the cores themselves thus tend to remain relatively clustered. The mass distribution of these cores appears to be similar to that of the initial mass function (IMF). The peak mass of the distribution is typically on the order of the Bonnor-Ebert mass.¹ The Bonner-Ebert mass only represents a good proxy for the fiducial masses of the cores. As such, there exists a wide range of masses.

The process by which these dense cores proceed to become protostars is not completely understood, but is believed to begin with the collapse of the core. If the core is not already in a state of collapse, collapse of the core can be achieved by the loss of support from a mass greater than the Jeans’ Mass.² The collapsing core creates a protostar that continues to increase in mass and temperature as more and more outer layers collapse. Material in the core that has not yet collapsed is referred to as the protostellar envelope. There is continual material infall from the protostellar envelope onto an accretion disk around the star. As the material falls in, angular momentum is conserved by the formation of massive energetic bipolar molecular outflows. These are observable and are indicators of active star formation (Shepherd & Churchwell, 1996).

¹The Bonnor-Ebert Mass is the mass threshold such that an isothermal gas sphere remains in hydrostatic equilibrium. Exceeding this mass leads to gravitational collapse. (i.e. to become a protostar)

²The Jeans’ Mass is the mass that, if exceeded by cloud, would collapse. This mass can be derived from comparing the gravitational and thermal energy in a spherical gas cloud as well as using Newton’s second law.

1.2 Rate of Star Formation

The mass of stars formed per unit time, or star formation rate (SFR), is a quantity that is immensely helpful in learning how stars form across time. In particular, the relationship between the SFR and the amount of gas is crucial in understanding how local environments and properties affect the process of star formation. Attempts to explain this relationship can trace its origins to Schmidt (1959) and Kennicutt (1989) where a power law relation between the gas density and the SFR in a local region was proposed. Kennicutt (1998) furthered this concept by suggesting that this power law is applicable to a range of gas densities over a variety of spatial scales. However, recent observations of star formation at smaller scales and higher redshifts, such as those by Heiderman et al. (2010) and Daddi et al. (2010), have found that the relationship seems to be more complex. Observations of the nearest molecular clouds (within 1 kpc) show star formation rate surface densities 10 times greater than in larger, beam-averaged extragalactic regions (Evans et al., 2009; Lada et al., 2010; Heiderman et al., 2010). More distant observations of disk and starburst galaxies in the local regions as well as at high redshifts by Daddi et al. (2010) and Genzel et al. (2010) found starburst galaxies exhibiting star formation at factors of approximately 10 higher than disk galaxies despite having an identical gas surface density. These studies suggest that local properties, such as gas density, may not be the only parameters that affect the star formation. Instead, larger-scale variations such as distance to the center of the galaxy may need to be considered.

There have been recent attempts to reconcile this seemingly more complex relationship. Krumholz et al. (2012) suggests a simple, local, volumetric star formation law where the star formation rate is simply ≈ 1 percent of the molecular gas per local free-fall time while Lada et al. (2012) suggests another simple relation: where the the total star formation rate of a molecular cloud is linearly proportional to the total mass of dense gas in that cloud above a density threshold of $116 M_{\odot} \text{pc}^{-2}$.

Although it is generally agreed that the SFR increases as the gas density and/or mass

Figure 1.1: Relation between Star Formation Rate and Total Gas Surface Densities from Bigiel et al. (2008). While the precise nature of the relationship is unclear, it is generally agreed upon that the SFR increases as gas density increases. Different environments are indicated by the various symbols. Environments range from starburst galaxies to low-surface-brightness galaxies. Some variation can be seen between star formation rates of different environments.

increases (see 1.1), the precise nature of the relationship is still unclear. Observations of the star-forming regions at smaller spatial scales (≤ 100 pc) are mostly relegated to those in the solar neighborhood or in nearby spiral galaxies. These regions have fairly similar environments and thus do not allow for a significant amount of leverage in measuring the relationship between SFR and dense gas. The closest region with a notably different environment is the central molecular zone (CMZ). It is for this reason that the CMZ was observed in the SMA Legacy Survey. The CMZ offers a sufficiently different environment to be another point of comparison.

1.3 Central Molecular Zone

The central molecular zone (CMZ) is a region near the center of the Milky Way located approximately in the innermost 500 pc of the Galaxy. The region is characterized by high densities, large velocity dispersions, high temperatures, and strong magnetic fields. The region only includes a couple percent of the Galaxy’s total molecular gas content, but contains approximately 80% of its dense molecular gas content, with densities 1 to 2 orders of magnitude above that in the Galactic disk. The gas temperature in the CMZ is higher in comparison to gas temperatures in the Galactic disk as well as the dust temperature in the CMZ. While the dust temperature of the CMZ is approximately 15 K, the gas in the CMZ have a typical gas temperature of 70 K, but temperatures have been observed to reach as high as 150 K. (Rodriguez-Fernandez et al., 2002) Larger typical line-widths of the GMCs in comparison to those in the disk also suggest large internal motions within these GMCs in the CMZ.

Given this environment, the initial starting conditions for star formation differ greatly from the rest of the Galaxy. Motions of the gas and dust in the CMZ are believed to be the result of two ‘families’ of orbits in the Galactic center: X_1 and X_2 . The X_1 and X_2 are described by their position with regards to the corotation circle of the Galaxy, the region

Figure 1.2: Simulations of Contopoulos & Mertzanides (1977) from Binney et al. (1991). The first panel shows the X_1 and X_2 orbits in space. In this top down view, the x and y axis are representative of physical distances. The X_1 orbit are indicated by the solid lines while the X_2 orbits are represented by the dashed lines at the center. The middle and right one show the l, v (longitude, velocity) plots from the angle of the dotted and dashed lines that extend from the center of the first panel respectively. In addition to the intersection points of X_1 and X_2 orbits, certain X_1 orbits can be seen to intersect themselves. Intersections of X_1 orbits and itself can be observed near the vertical ‘tips’ of the first panel. The locations are likely the sites of collisions and possible star formation.

where stars orbit at the same speed as the spiral arms as well as the Lindblad resonance³. The X_1 orbits are found outside the inner Lindblad resonance, but inside the corotation circle and thus are oriented to be aligned to the bar of the galaxy. X_2 orbits are found inside the inner Lindblad resonance and are oriented perpendicular to the bar. The X_1 orbits extend around 1.2 kpc out to connect with the galactic disk and intersect with the X_2 orbits at approximately 200 pc. This intersection point is the center of many collisions between molecular clouds and leads X_2 orbits to contain the densest and most turbulent GMCs in the galaxy. It is in these X_2 orbits that the most active star formation in the galaxy occurs. The highly active “100 pc ring” is believed to be part of these X_2 orbits. However, given the enormous reservoir of dense gas in the region, the star formation is still less than that predicted by models. Figure 1.2 show nested simulations of orbits based on Contopoulos & Mertzaniades (1977). The intersection of the X_1 and X_2 orbits seen are potential locations for collisions.

Kruijssen, Dale, and Longmore (2015) proposed an extension and/or alternative to replace the X_2 orbit of the previous models, suggesting four streams of open orbits, as seen in Figure 1.3. This new model is obtained by fitting models to empirical data. Six input orbital parameters such as apocenter and pericenter radii are varied to obtain the best fit orbital model for the observed position–velocity distribution of dense gas from the H₂O southern Galactic Plane Survey. Kruijssen, Dale, and Longmore’s model differs from the earlier model mentioned above as it involves higher orbital velocities as well as places Sgr A* at the focus of the orbit. It is also more consistent than any previous models with regards to observational properties, such as the 3D space velocities of clusters, not initially included in the theory’s formulation.

The central 100 parsecs of the CMZ is believed to contain episodic bursts of star formation. Despite the low SFR relative to the amount of dense gas, there is evidence of a recent star formation event. In addition, the presence of older stars indicate even earlier star

³Lindblad resonance is a an orbital resonance present in sprial galaxies where the galaxy’s epicyclic frequency is some multiple of the forced frequency. See Sellwood (2013) for additional information.

Figure 1.3: The model proposed in Kruijssen, Dale, and Longmore 2015. The active star-forming X_2 orbit at approximately 100 pc includes an open orbit with four independent gas streams in this model rather than the typical closed orbit.

formation events have also taken place. Torrey et al. (2016) suggest a feedback regulated mechanism by which this may occur. Given the stronger star-formation inhibiting conditions, such as higher temperature and turbulence, a higher than average density is needed for stars to form. This can be achieved by the continual increase in density from radial inflow of gas from the X_1 orbits, until the density required is attained. Once this occurs, star-formation occurs until a critical mass of stars are formed. At this point, feedback from these newly formed stars, blow gas and dust from the region until the density is no longer high enough for star formation. From here, the cycle repeats as new gas from the X_1 orbits flow in. Thus, it is believed that the central 100 parsecs of the CMZ is a location of periodic bursts of star formation. Other locations of star formation include the large and dense Sgr B2 and Sgr C clouds each located approximately 100 pc from Sgr A*.

The clouds of the CMZ are similar in properties (such as gas surface density) to those in high-redshift starburst galaxies that are undergoing star formation (Kruijssen & Longmore, 2013). Recent observations by Longmore et al. (2013), however, indicate a lower than expected SFR in the CMZ (by approximately one order of magnitude). Several factors are believed to be the cause. These include the possibility of magnetic fields, high gas temperature, or turbulence affecting the nature of these clouds which can disrupt the formation of cores and thus the formation of stars. It is also possible that the region exhibits episodic star formation that varies with time like that observed in the central 100 pc. It is unclear, however, which factor is the most crucial in contributing to the observed discrepancy.

In this study, I focus on two regions outside of the immediate central 100 pc region of the CMZ. The first is G1.602+0.018 located in what is referred to as the $l = 1.6^\circ$ complex, or 1.6 Degree Cloud. Existing literature (Rodríguez-Fernández, 2006) regarding G1.602+0.018 suggests that the cloud is located at the intersection of high longitude X_1 orbits and the 100 pc streams.

The second is a larger cloud located at approximately $l = 1.1^\circ$, known as the 1.1 Degree Cloud. Figure 1.5 indicates the second region to be studied. Like the 1.6 Degree Cloud, the

Figure 1.4: The two regions examined in this study are boxed above. Within the yellow and blue box is the 1.6 Degree Cloud and the 1.1 Degree Cloud respectively. The image is composed of $N(H_2)$ (red) from blackbody fits to Herschel (Battersby et al., 2011), $70 \mu m$ (green) emission from PACS (Pilbratt et al., 2010), and $8 \mu m$ (blue) emission from Spitzer IRS (Houck et al., 2004).

region is removed from the 100 pc region and is not expected to contain star formation based on that fact alone. Each occupies a different location and thus environment in the orbits of the CMZ. Examining each would allow for comparison of similarities and differences that may arise as a result.

Observational data from the Submillimeter Array (SMA) located in Manua Kea, Hawaii will be used in examining the 1.1 Degree and 1.6 Degree Cloud. Both new and archival data from the survey are included from the three-year SMA Legacy Survey. The dust continuum images and spectral line emission of each region will be examined and supplemented with single dish data.

This study seeks to shed light on the nature of star formation in the various parts of the CMZ and how the various environmental factors play a role. In addition, this study can provide a resource to guide future work that incorporates the use of this survey data. Eventually, in combination with other studies, this may answer the greater question of the observed suppressed star formation in the CMZ.

Figure 1.5: Map of the 1.1 Degree Cloud. The 1.1 Degree Cloud is shown in the magenta contour overlaid with green circles. The green circles are the mosaic pointings from the Submillimeter Array. The image is a column density ($N(H_2)$) map created from Herschel data. The magenta contour, including the one that outlines the 1.1 Degree Cloud is $1 \times 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The light blue and dark blue contour are $1 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $5 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

Chapter 2

Observations and Data

2.1 Submillimeter Array Legacy Survey Data

The Submillimeter Array (SMA) is a radio interferometer located on Manua Kea, Hawaii. Operational in 2004, the SMA's eight six-meter diameter antennas became the first purpose-built submillimeter interferometer. Laid out on a Reuleaux triangle for optimal sampling, the SMA was configured for an elliptical beam with an average angular resolution of approximately 4" for this survey.

The SMA Legacy Survey is a three-year program designed to survey the CMZ. Taking both 1.3 mm dust continuum and spectral line data, the survey is in the process of mapping roughly 240 arcmin² of the CMZ.

One of the guiding questions of the SMA Legacy Survey is the SFR and understanding why the SFR is substantially lower than expected. Understanding this would allow us to revise our laws of star formation. In addition, the survey hopes to further reveal the nature of the larger scale flows of mass and gas in the CMZ. This is in hopes of observing any evidence of periodic or cyclic nature in the star formation in the center of the Galaxy. If periodic star formation is present in the CMZ, this could explain the lower than expected SFR that is observed. The final question of interest is to see what the role of various orbits

and mass streams is in inducing or inhibiting star formation. The SMA Legacy Survey would be critical in considering the model set forth in Contopoulos & Mertzaniades (1977) as well as Kruijssen et al. (2015). In addition, the SMA Legacy Survey addresses several other questions that are not specifically focused on in this study. These include the examination of massive stars and their precursors, as well as the $l = 1.3$ degree complex and its interaction with the 100 pc ring.

The SMA is especially suited for this survey due to its combination of large primary beam ($\sim 50''$), high angular resolution, and large bandwidth. As a result of this, the survey's observation of the continuum at 1.3mm is able to detect and catalog star-forming cores and find locations of high-mass star formation. In addition, simultaneous taking of spectral data allows the use of SiO outflows, shocked gas, and other tracers to further determine the nature of the cores. Determination of parameters such as line widths of various spectral lines can be used to observe the amount of turbulence as well as investigate virial masses of these cores.

Observations were done in both 4 GHz sidebands, with the higher centered at 230.9 GHz and the lower centered at 218.9 GHz. Figure 2.1 shows the configuration of the SMA's correlator with the various key molecules that can be observed. These includes various transitions of formaldehyde (H_2CO) as well as ^{12}CO , ^{13}CO , C^{18}O , SiO, CH_3OH , and CH_3CN . Figure 2.2b shows the progress as of November 2015. Completed mosaic pointings are shown in open green circles in the top image with all planned pointings, also shown in open green circles, in the bottom. Open red circles indicated completed mosaic pointings from a previous study of the CMZ.

Data used from the SMA Legacy Survey includes that taken in both Year 1 and Year 2 of the survey. The 1.6 Degree Cloud was observed in June and July of 2014 (Year 1 of the SMA Legacy Survey) in both compact and subcompact configurations. The 1.1 degree cloud was observed in Year 2 of the SMA Legacy Survey in April and May of 2015 in both compact and subcompact as well. The compact configuration provided a maximum baseline and angular resolution of 87.31 m and $3.85''$ respectively. The subcompact configuration

Figure 2.1: The bands covered by the SMA Legacy Survey are shown with key molecular transitions. The LSB and USB indicated refers the lower side band and upper side band respectively.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2.2: (a) Progress of the survey as of November 2015. Positions in open green circles have been observed. (b) All of the planned observations of the three-year SMA Legacy Survey. Red circles indicated refer to data taken before the beginning of the SMA Legacy Survey. The image is a column density ($N(H_2)$) map created from Herschel data. The magenta contour, including the one that outlines the 1.1 Degree Cloud, is $1 \times 10^{23} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The light blue and dark blue contour are $1 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $5 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ respectively.

provided a minimum baseline and resolution of 9.48 m and 35.44" respectively. Data used in this study includes data in both the compact and subcompact configuration for the 1.6 Degree Cloud, but only in the compact configuration for the 1.1 Degree Cloud.

2.2 Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey Data

Data from the SMA Legacy Survey is supplemented with data from the Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey (BGPS). Bolocam, a large-format bolometric camera made for observations at 2.1 mm as well as at 1.1 mm, was installed on the 10.4 m Caltech Submillimeter Observatory located in Manua Kea, Hawaii. The BGPS is a 1.1 mm continuum survey of the northern Galactic Plane. The coverage includes 170 square degrees, comprised of the contiguous region from $-10.5 \leq l \leq 90.5$ degrees and $-0.5 \leq b \leq 0.5$ degrees as well as several other specific regions. The second release of the BGPS's 1.1 mm continuum data (Ginsburg et al., 2013) was used. A flux calibration error present in the initial one was corrected for in this subsequent release.

Although the SMA Legacy Survey is conducted in two configurations, the nature of interferometry is such that it is unable to capture much of the large scale structure and flux. Using single dish data from the BGPS, these structures can be recovered. Additionally, interferometry produces artifacts due to incomplete sampling of certain spatial frequencies. This can also be effectively reduced by combining with the single dish data. The 1.1 mm data is reconciled with the 1.3 mm SMA data by assuming a β value for the spectral energy distribution and then feathering¹ the two data sets together. In this study, we assumed the value of $\beta = 2$. Figure 2.3 shows the effect of incorporating both single dish and interferometry data. There are significantly less artifacts and some additional large-scale flux was recovered.

The data reduction and feathering process is further described in Chapter 3.

¹Feathering refers to the process of combining two images with different spatial resolution together. Feathering is discussed further in Section 3.2.

Figure 2.3: Images of the 1.6 Degree Cloud show the effect of the addition of data at different spatial scales. Note the lack of small-scale detail in the image consisting only of SMA Subcompact Data and the lack of large-scale structure in the image consisting of the SMA Compact Data. The combination show a clear improvement, with the structure and detail both being present. The addition of the single dish data from the BGPS further improve the image and noticeably recovers large-scale flux.

2.3 Atacama Pathfinder EXperiment Data

Spectral line data from the SMA Survey was supplemented with single dish spectral line data from the Atacama Pathfinder EXperiment (APEX). Located in the Andes mountain in Chile, APEX is a 12 m diameter Atacama Large Millimeter Array (ALMA) telescope modified for single dish use. Designed to be the ‘pathfinder’ for other submillimeter surveys and observations, it became operational in 2005

APEX provides data in the lower sideband velocity channels with a resolution of 1 km/s while SMA data is provided in 1.1 km/s. Reconciling and feathering the data here is done channel by channel using various Python scripts. This is also further discussed in Chapter 3.

Chapter 3

Data Reduction and Processing

3.1 Submillimeter Array Legacy Survey Data

Interferometry data, including that provided by the SMA is provided in its raw form as samplings of the sky. These are amplitude and phase measurements between baselines of each pair of antennas at each moment in time. In this raw uncalibrated form the data exists as Fourier transforms of brightness of the sky at each point. In order to be analyzed, the data must first be calibrated. In this process, the raw visibilities are processed in order to compensate for any physical sources of error. These include fluctuations in the electronics, such as the system temperature and antenna efficiencies. System temperature was calibrated for using an ambient load on a chopper wheel. Phase-based gain calibrations was done in order to correct for variations in the atmosphere that may occur during the course of observing. To correct for any variations in the receivers, a bandpass calibration was done. A source of known flux, such as Titan or Neptune, is also observed to make final flux calibrations. This process is completed using the MIR environment, a software package created to process radio interferometry data, in IDL.¹

Next, MIRIAD is used to prepare the dataset for use in the CASA (Common Astronomy

¹The calibration was not completed by the author. More information regarding the calibration procedure, as well as the MIR package, can be found at <https://www.cfa.harvard.edu/~cqi/mircook.html>

Software Applications) software package. MIRIAD converts the MIR-processed SMA data to a format suitable for CASA. As both the spectral line data as well as the dust continuum data are of interest, MIRIAD is used to separate the two from the overall dataset. In addition, this separated data is divided into smaller chunks for faster processing in CASA.

This calibrated and separated dataset is then ready for imaging. This process is completed in CASA. Although calibrated, the data remains Fourier transforms of the sky. In order for an image to be created, the visibilities are first deconvolved from a map of visibilities to measurements of the sky’s true brightness. This results in a “dirty image”. This image contains the true sky brightness, but is also convolved with a point source function (PSF) or the “dirty beam”. This dirty beam is essentially the beam pattern. In order to deconvolve the “dirty beam” and produce the final “clean” image, a process known as cleaning is done.

The CLEAN procedure is the most widely used method of deconvolution in radio astronomy and is used in this study. It is a nonlinear iterative process that uses the known shape of the “dirty beam” in order to separate and distinguish between the real structure of the image and the sidelobes of the “dirty beam”. Assuming that the image can be approximated as a collection of point sources, the algorithm begins by selecting the highest peak in the dirty image and removing the “dirty beam” centered and convolved at that point. This step is repeated until some user-specified level is reached. The user-specified threshold is important in preventing “overcleaning”. In this study, the threshold is approximated by finding the RMS of the image. Assuming the noise of the image is roughly Gaussian, we treat the RMS of the image as the standard deviation (σ). The threshold is chosen to be 3σ or approximately three times the RMS. The image is then restored by adding back all the peaks, or the “clean components”, but reconvolved with the “clean beam”. The “clean beam” is produced by fitting a Gaussian beam to the “dirty beam”.

Various different CLEAN algorithms exist. The one used in this study is known as the Clark method from Clark (1980). This method is similar to the basic CLEAN algorithm as outlined above. The Clark method differs in being more efficient through the introduction of

a major and minor cycle in order to locate the highest peak without progressing through the entire CLEAN step. This reduces the necessary computational effort and thus time. Due to the subjective nature of the cleaning process, the number of iterations and cycle varies by individual case. Cleaning in CASA also allowed for interactive selection of areas to be cleaned thus increasing the speed by which the algorithm operates.

CLEAN algorithms are not the only method of cleaning and deconvolving radio astronomy data. Other methods include the maximum entropy method (MEM) and non-negative-least-squares (NNLS) method as well as more recent ones such as Adaptive Scale Pixel (ASP) and RESOLVE, a new algorithm involving information field theory and Bayesian statistics. Due to the variations in the data in radio interferometry as well as the non-linear effects of the cleaning process, some methods of cleaning produce better results than others.

3.2 Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey Data

Dust continuum data from the BGPS is included as the single dish contribution. After the cleaning of the SMA data is complete, the FEATHER function within CASA was used to feather and combine the data with interferometry data from the SMA. This procedure converts each image to the visibility plane and combines them. They are then reconverted back to become the combined image. The results of combining the data is as shown in Figure 2.3.

3.3 Atacama Pathfinder EXperiment Data

Single dish data from APEX is also feathered with the SMA data. While the feather process is comparable to that of the continuum data it is complicated by the need to regrid all the data in the frequency space as well. As such, a more sophisticated procedure involving Python scripts making use of CASA functions is employed to feather the single dish and interferometry data. Two different methods were used and tested to feather the two sets of

data.

The first Python routine used is based off a script created by Mark Graham (Graham, 2015). For each spectral line, a dirty image using only the SMA spectral data is created. Next, APEX single dish data is prepared. This includes regridding single dish's coordinate system and scaling the data's units. During the cleaning process, the single dish data is incorporated. The cleaning process includes several coarse and finer stages of cleaning before being feathered to produce the final spectral line data cube. The second method used is a pipeline created by Jens Kauffman² from the Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy. This method differs from the former by not including any interactive cleaning steps as well as implementing steps in a different order. While Mark Graham's procedure interspersed the removing of masked and negative points in the SMA data between several steps of coarse and fine cleaning, Jens Kauffman completed the removal of masked and negative points after one implementation of CLEAN. This also means that more steps of cleaning were implemented in Mark Graham's procedure. Both pipelines produced data cubes with two spatial dimensions and a third for the velocity channels.

In practice, this has resulted in Jens Kauffman's pipeline being requiring less computing time to complete. Thus, that pipeline was chosen to produce the images for this study. However, the full implications and differences of reordering the steps is difficult to gauge. The lack of the interactive cleaning steps suggests that the cleaning may not be as efficient. Initial comparisons of images produced by this study and those produced by Mark Graham in Graham (2015) indicates the addition of an interactive cleaning step may improve quality.

²Available at <http://tinyurl.com/zero-spacing>

Chapter 4

Methods

Data from both the dust continuum and spectral lines will be used to estimate and derive several properties and parameters for the 1.6 Degree Cloud and 1.1 Degree Cloud. The 1.6 Degree Cloud was observed over one night in 2014 and previously imaged in Graham (2015). The 1.1 Degree Cloud was observed over four nights in 2015.

4.1 Mass Estimates

4.1.1 Submillimeter Array Dust Estimate

Using the feathered dust continuum data from the Submillimeter Array and BGPS, a 2D Gaussian is fit over each individual source. A visual search is done to identify clear and obvious sources, before the 2D Gaussian fit is done using CASA. Integrating the flux beneath the fit results in the integrated flux density of the source. Using this value, it is possible to find a dust mass estimate using:

$$M = \frac{S_\nu D^2}{\kappa_\nu B_\nu(T)} \quad (4.1)$$

Here S_ν is the integrated flux density, D is the distance, κ_ν is the dust opacity, and $B_\nu(T)$ is the blackbody function at a temperature (T). The distance D is given to be the distance from the Earth to the Galactic center. From Paczyński & Stanek (1998), this value is set to be 8.4 ± 0.4 kpc. As in Battersby et al. (2010), we assume a dust-to-gas ratio of 100. The dust opacity is derived from tabulated opacity values at various wavelengths. From Ossenkopf & Henning (1994), at 1.3 mm, the dust opacity value (κ) is $0.899 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ in dust. Assuming a MRN grain size distribution with thin ice mantles and a gas density of 10^6 cm^{-3} , we find the spectral index to be 2. Using this and the dust-to-gas ratio of 100, we scale and estimate the opacity at 1.335 mm to be $0.00899 \text{ cm}^2/\text{g}$ for H_2 . Dust temperature estimates were estimated to be 15 K, as estimated in Graham (2015), for the 1.6 Degree Cloud and 18 K for the 1.1 Degree Cloud. These dust temperatures are based on measurements made from Herschel blackbody fits in Battersby (in prep.). Ginsburg et al. (2015) estimated gas temperatures of the CMZ from ~ 60 K to 100 K, but also concluded the gas temperature to be universally higher than that of the dust. As the SMA observations were made at 1.3 mm of the dust, the dust temperature estimated from the Herschel blackbody fits in Battersby (in prep.) were used.

4.1.2 Virial Mass Estimate

The virial mass can be compared to the estimated dust mass in order to estimate whether or not the cores are bound. The virial ratio (α_{vir}) is defined as the ratio of the virial mass to dust mass. A $\alpha_{\text{vir}} < 1$ indicates that the mass estimated from the dust continuum exceeds the virial mass suggesting that the core may be in equilibrium, self-gravitating, and bound. If $\alpha_{\text{vir}} > 1$, the mass estimated from the dust continuum does not exceed the virial mass, suggesting that the cores are not virialized, and thus, does not suggest the core to be star-forming.

The virial mass can be estimated from using molecular line widths from the spectral line data. Assuming the core is in fact gravitationally bound and in virial equilibrium such that

the line is broadened only by virialized motion, the mass can be derived using the virial theorem. Assuming a density profile of $\rho(r) = r^{-\alpha}$, the mass of a core is given by:¹

$$M_{\text{vir}} = 4 \left(\frac{5 - 2\alpha}{3 - \alpha} \right) \frac{R_{\text{vir}} \sigma^2}{G} \quad (4.2)$$

where α is the spectral index of the density profile, G is the gravitational constant, R_{vir} is the virial radius, and σ is the line-of-sight velocity dispersion. Assuming that the spectral index is $\alpha = 2$, we can relate σ to the full width half maximum of the molecular line width using a Gaussian expression. Doing so, the expression becomes:

$$M_{\text{vir}} = 126 \frac{R_{\text{vir}}}{1 \text{ pc}} \left(\frac{\Delta v_{\text{FWHM}}}{1 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right)^2 M_{\odot} \quad (4.3)$$

The R_{vir} is calculated from two-dimensional elliptical Gaussian fits. Assuming the cores are compact and spherical, the full width at half maximum major (B_{maj}^2) and minor axis (B_{min}^2) of the fit is used to approximate the R_{vir} using $R_{\text{vir}} = \sqrt{(B_{\text{maj}}^2 + B_{\text{min}}^2)/8}$.

4.2 Surface Density

Surface density can also be used to investigate the possibility of star formation in cores. Krumholz & McKee (2008) showed that a theoretical minimum column density of 1 g/cm^2 is necessary for massive stars ($M > 8M_{\odot}$) to form. Above that threshold, the core is able collapse and avoid fragmentation. However, it is possible for smaller stars to be formed from a core with a column density less than 1 g/cm^2 . The surface density can be calculated by converting the units of Jy/beam into a mass surface density. Using the methods for estimating the dust mass shown above, a value of mass per beam was derived. The beam area was found by finding the area of the elliptical gaussian using the full width half maximum (FWHM) values of the major and minor axis of the beam. Where s_{ν} is the individual flux

¹The full derivation of this equation is available in Appendix A.1.

at each pixel and B_{maj} and B_{min} are the full width half max values in degrees:

$$\rho_s = \left[\frac{s_\nu D^2}{\kappa_\nu B_\nu T} \right] \left[\left(\frac{\pi}{4 \ln 2} \right) D^2 \tan(B_{\text{maj}}) \tan(B_{\text{min}}) \right]^{-1} \quad (4.4)$$

For the 1.6 Degree Cloud, this reduces to:

$$\rho_s = s_\nu \times (2.334 \times 10^{24}) \quad \text{g/cm}^2 \quad (4.5)$$

For the 1.1 Degree Cloud, this becomes:

$$\rho_s = s_\nu \times (3.88 \times 10^{24}) \quad \text{g/cm}^2 \quad (4.6)$$

4.3 N-PDFs

N-PDFs are the column density probability distribution function and are common methods of analyzing and determining whether a molecular cloud is star-forming. A cloud well-characterized by a lognormal distribution indicates a cloud without star-formation while clouds with a power-law tail are actively star-forming (Kainulainen et al., 2009). A cloud with a lognormal distribution can be interpreted to have turbulent motions dominating its dynamics. The wider the distribution, the higher the Mach number of the turbulence (Ballesteros-Paredes et al., 2011). Alternatively, if a region's distribution includes the presence of a power-law tail at high column densities, this implies that the cloud contains self-gravitating regions that may be star-forming. From Ballesteros-Paredes et al. (2011), numerical simulations have shown that as local and global collapse occurs, the number of high column density points increases and produces the signature power-law tail. In addition, empirical evidence has shown that the power-law tail has only ever been seen in N-PDFs of clouds that contain star-formation. (Ballesteros-Paredes et al., 2011)

N-PDFs are produced for both the 1.6 Degree and 1.1 Degree Cloud. A Python script

was developed to import the dust continuum image FITS file from each region as an array of values encoding the flux per beam at each pixel. This value at each pixel is then converted to a column density ($N(H_2)$). $N(H_2)$ can be measured as:

$$N(H_2) = \frac{s_\nu}{\Omega_A \mu_{H_2} m_H \kappa_\nu B_\nu(T)} \quad (4.7)$$

where Ω_A is the beam size, μ_{H_2} is the mean molecular weight of H_2 , m_H is the mass of hydrogen, and κ_ν is the opacity. $B_\nu(T)$ is again the blackbody function at a temperature (T). Replacing with constants and converting to typical units:

$$N(H_2) = (2.02 \times 10^{20} \text{cm}^{-2}) \left(e^{1.439(\lambda/\text{mm})^{-1}(T/10)^{-1}} - 1 \right) \times \left(\frac{\kappa_\nu}{0.01 \text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}} \right)^{-1} \left(\frac{s_\nu}{\text{mJy Beam}^{-1}} \right) \left(\frac{\theta_{\text{HPBW}}}{10 \text{arcsec}} \right)^{-2} \left(\frac{\lambda}{\text{mm}} \right)^3 \text{cm}^{-2} \quad (4.8)$$

where $\pi\theta_{\text{HPBW}} = \pi \left(\sqrt{(B_{\text{maj}}^2 + B_{\text{min}}^2)/2} \right)$. Since each value can be obtained by multiplying by a scalar, we can simply write:

$$N(H_2) \propto \left[\left(e^{(\lambda T)^{-1}} - 1 \right) \kappa_\nu^{-1} \theta_{\text{HPBW}}^{-2} \lambda^3 \right] s_\nu \quad (4.9)$$

where the portion within the brackets is the scalar. Once the values have been converted to column density, each value is then sorted and binned to produce a histogram distribution. Fitting a lognormal curve, we can then observe the behavior of the regions distribution. A lower limit is established for the fitting, approximately at $1 - \sigma$, and thus excludes the insignificant and low column density values.

Chapter 5

Results

5.1 1.6 Degree Cloud: G1.602+0.018

The cloud known as the 1.6 Degree Cloud is located at G1.602+0.018. The area imaged by the SMA is approximately 58 square parsecs and encloses a mass of approximately $1.6 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$ (Graham, 2015) and approximated to have a temperature of 15 K (Battersby in prep.).

Figure 5.1 shows an image of the dust continuum produced from compact and subcompact SMA data feathered with single-dish APEX data. Two isolated cores are visible. Core 1, as indicated in figure 5.1, is estimated to have a dust mass of approximately $620 M_{\odot}$ at a dust temperature of 15 K. Elliptical Gaussian fitting estimates a mean deconvolved radius of approximately 0.17 pc. Virial mass is estimated to be approximately $530 M_{\odot}$. This provides a $\alpha_{\text{vir}} = 0.85$. The peak surface density for Core 1 is calculated to be 1.0 g/cm^2 . Core 2, also indicated in figure 5.1, is estimated to have a dust mass of approximately $200 M_{\odot}$, smaller than Core 1. Elliptical Gaussian fitting estimates a mean deconvolved radius of approximately 0.21 pc. Virial mass is estimated to be approximately $320 M_{\odot}$ resulting in a $\alpha_{\text{vir}} = 1.6$. The peak surface density for Core 2 is calculated to be 0.7 g/cm^2 . Fits of the H_2CO line at 218.222 GHz of each core respectively are shown in figure 5.3. A integrated

G1.602+0.018				
Core	Dust Mass	Virial Mass	Virial Ratio (α_{vir})	
1	620 M_{\odot}	530 M_{\odot}	0.85	
2	200 M_{\odot}	320 M_{\odot}	1.6	
	Integrated Flux	Mean Radius	Peak Surface Density	
1	0.25 Jy	0.17 pc	1.0 g/cm ²	
2	0.08 Jy	0.21 pc	0.7 g/cm ²	

Table 5.1: Parameters for the 1.6 Degree Cloud.

intensity map for H₂CO is seen in figure 5.6. Figure 5.4 shows the N-PDF for G1.602+0.018. The parameters of the fit are a standard deviation of $\sigma_n = 0.18$ with the peak at 3.4×10^{22} cm⁻². The lower limit of the fit is limited to $1 - \sigma$ at 1.6×10^{22} cm⁻². All data points above that point are used in fitting. The lognormal fit fits the histogram fairly well. There is a power law deviation that suggests the cores may be self-gravitating on the high end slope. This information is summarized in Table 5.1.

5.2 1.1 Degree Cloud: G0.891-0.048

The cloud known as the 1.1 Degree Cloud located at G0.891-0.048 is substantially larger than the 1.6 Degree Cloud. Observing of the 1.1 Degree Cloud required four nights of observation in the compact configuration. The 1.1 Degree Cloud is shown in Figure 5.2. One isolated core is visible. Using the approximated dust temperature of 18 K for the 1.1 Degree Cloud, the dust mass is approximated to have a dust mass of approximately 770 M_{\odot} . Line widths were measured to be 1.3 km/s. Virial mass is estimated to be approximately 85 M_{\odot} . This provides a $\alpha_{\text{vir}} = 0.11$. The peak surface density for Core 1 is calculated to be 0.4 g/cm². Elliptical Gaussian fitting estimates a mean radius of approximately 0.4 pc. Figure 5.5 shows the N-PDF for the 1.1 Degree Cloud. The parameters of the fit are a standard deviation of $\sigma_n = 0.12$ with the peak at 2.1×10^{22} cm⁻². There is no clear power-law tail.

G0.891-0.048			
Core	Dust Mass	Virial Mass	Virial Ratio (α_{vir})
1	$770 M_{\odot}$	$85 M_{\odot}$	0.11
	Integrated Flux	Mean Radius	Peak Surface Density
1	0.39 Jy	0.4 pc	0.4 g/cm^2

Table 5.2: Parameters for the 1.1 Degree Cloud.

This information is summarized in Table 5.2

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.1: Dust continuum image of 1.6 Degree Cloud. This image is feathered with single dish data provided by the Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey. Detailed parameters of each core is shown in table 5.1. The RMS noise (σ) is determine by averaging the RMS of small boxed regions near the edge of the image away from any significant emission. For this image, $\sigma = 3.95$ mJy/Beam. Contours visible in 5.1b are 3σ , 7σ , and 10σ . The grey ellipse visible in the lower left corner of both images represent the beam size and shape.

Figure 5.2: Dust continuum image of the 1.1 Degree Cloud. This image is feathered with single dish data provided by the Bolocam Galactic Plane Survey. Detailed parameters of each core is shown in table 5.2. The RMS noise (σ) is determine by averaging the RMS of small boxed regions near the edge of the image away from any significant emission. For this image, $\sigma = 4.3$ mJy/Beam. Contours visible in 5.2b are 3σ , 7σ , and 10σ . The grey ellipse visible in the lower left corner of both images represent the beam size and shape.

(a) Core 1

(b) Core 2

Figure 5.3: Fits of H_2CO line at 218.222 GHz for each of the two cores observed in the 1.6 Degree Cloud. The x -axis is frequency as radio velocity in km/s and the y -axis gives the flux in Jy/beam.

Figure 5.4: Column Density PDF of the 1.6 Degree Cloud. Data points above the lower limit of $1.6 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ ($1 - \sigma$) are used to fit the data. The dotted lines represents the data used to fit the lognormal curve. The parameters of the fit are a standard deviation of $\sigma_n = 0.18$ with the peak at $3.4 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The dashed line between the dotted lines represents the $3\text{-}\sigma$ value.

Figure 5.5: Column Density PDF of the 1.1 Degree Cloud. Data points above the lower limit of $1.4 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ ($1 - \sigma$) are used to fit the data. The dotted lines represents the data used to fit the lognormal curve. The parameters of the fit are a standard deviation of $\sigma_n = 0.12$ with the peak at $2.1 \times 10^{22} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. The dashed line between the dotted lines represents the $3\text{-}\sigma$ value.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.6: Integrated Intensity of H_2CO in the 1.6 Degree Cloud. Rings indicate approximate locations of each core. Figure 5.3 shows line fittings obtained from fitting over where cores exist.

Chapter 6

Discussion

6.1 1.6 Degree Cloud: G1.602+0.018

The 1.6 Degree Cloud at G1.602+0.018 is observed to have two cores. The larger of which has a virial ratio of less than one suggesting it may be a site of a forming star or stars. Calculated from a H₂CO line, this is an indication that the core is unstable and may collapse. In addition the cloud's N-PDF contains a possible power law tail, supporting the suggestion that the 1.602 cloud is potentially star-forming. Graham (2015) finds similar conclusions, but calculated a $\alpha_{\text{vir}} < 1$ suggesting not just one, but both, cores are unstable and will collapse. Core 2 was found to have a $\alpha_{\text{vir}} = 1.6$ and a dust estimated mass of $M = 200 M_{\odot}$, while Graham (2015) found $\alpha_{\text{vir}} = 0.4$ and a dust estimated mass of $M = 340 M_{\odot}$. The mean radius calculated was 0.21 pc compared to 0.13 pc from Graham (2015) resulting in a higher M_{vir} . A lower mass and higher virial mass was calculated, thus suggesting a different conclusion for Core 2. For Core 1, Graham (2015) also found the core to exhibit SiO bipolar outflows and the existence of CH₃OH hot core tracers; other indicators of a star-forming core. The parameters of the 1.6 Degree Cloud from Graham (2015) are summarized in Table 6.1.

Mass	$1.6 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$
Dense Gas Mass	$1.1 \times 10^5 M_{\odot}$
Density (Mean)	$5 \times 10^3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
Temperature (Mean)	15 K

Table 6.1: Parameters of the 1.6 Degree Cloud from Graham (2015).

Rodríguez-Fernández (2006) had suggested that the $l = 1.6^{\circ}$ complex may be the site of an intersection between high longitude X_1 orbits and the 100 pc streams. As a result, the turbulence and shocks in this area should inhibit star formation. Turbulence is thought to prevent gravitational collapse and so inhibit formation on the larger scales (Klessen & Glover, 2014). As there does, in fact, appear to be evidence of star formation it suggests that these large collisions of orbits and streams and their resulting shocks and turbulences have a more nuanced affect on star formation. In particular, these effects may produce temporary high density areas such that star formation, or perhaps just core formations, can occur on a smaller-scale.

6.2 1.1 Degree Cloud: G0.891-0.048

The 1.1 Degree Cloud is observed to have at least one core. The core has a virial ratio considerably less than one suggesting it to be a potential site of a forming star. Similar to the core described in the 1.6 Degree Cloud, this is indication that the core may undergo or is undergoing collapse. However, the surface density of 0.4 g/cm^2 is less than one, and thus does not support the formation of a massive star. Furthermore, inspection of the cloud’s N-PDF reveals no discernible power-law tail either. As such, it is fairly inconclusive as to the true star-forming nature and potential of the cloud.

Several unplanned abnormalities occurred during the observation of the 1.1 Degree Cloud. Of the four observation tracks that compose the 1.1 Cloud from the SMA Legacy Survey, one of these tracks exhibited substantially higher noise levels slowing down the calibration

process. In addition, due to technical issues, this track also included observation of the 1.1 Degree Cloud in an unplanned configuration. The placement of one antenna in a unplanned location led to a much higher baseline for that antenna and the others, thus observing at a different spatial scale. Figure 6.1 shows examples of similarly unideal antenna placements. The arrangement that impact this study is very similar, but not identical, to that of the left column where a single antenna is placed far from the others. Note the elliptical beam shape and existence of waves and ripples that negatively affect the image. This is in comparison to the right column, the planned configuration that has a more circular beam and a conventional beam pattern.

These factors must be taken into account when viewing the values obtained from this data. While the core noted here is very likely to be real, it is likely that further study of the 1.1 Degree Cloud is required in order to better characterize the star-forming nature and potential of the region. In particular, higher-resolution surveys may be able to reveal and resolve cores that are invisible in this study.

6.3 Errors

The systematic uncertainties far outweigh the statistical uncertainties in this study. From Battersby et al. (2010), the errors are estimated through Monte Carlo simulations. For the equations detailed in Chapter 4, a fractional uncertainty is assigned to each variable. A Monte Carlo simulation is performed by sampling the variables from a Gaussian distribution based on their individual errors assigned below. The error is then reported as the 68% confidence interval.

For temperature estimates, the uncertainty is assigned a value of 50% as, described in Dunham et al. (2010), the temperature of clouds typically range from 10-20 K. The uncertainty for flux density is assigned 10%, and the opacity is assigned an uncertainty of a factor of two. Battersby et al. (2010) finds that the 68% confidence interval for the calculated

Figure 6.1: Suboptimal Antenna Configurations of the SMA. The top row shows the physical arrangement of the antennas. The second row indicates the coverage of the antennas in the uv -plane as a result of those antenna arrangements. The third row shows the resulting beam. The arrangement that impact this study is very similar, but not identical, to that of the left column where a single antenna is placed far from the others. In that column, note the ripples and sidelobes visible in the resulting beam. The placement of antenna 17 is the source of these features that are detrimental to the image.

Variable	Assigned Fractional Uncertainty
Temperature (1.6 Cloud)	50%
Temperature (1.1 Cloud)	50%
Flux Density	10%
Integrated Flux	10%
Dust Mass	80% - 180%

Table 6.2: Dust Mass Uncertainty and Errors

Variable	Assigned Fractional Uncertainty
Line Width	20%
Virial Mass	50% - 170%

Table 6.3: Virial Mass Uncertainty and Errors

dust continuum mass range from approximately 80% to 180%.

Estimated virial masses include several unquantifiable uncertainties. Calculation of the virial mass includes the implicit assumption that the core is gravitationally bound. This assumption has no quantifiable uncertainty. Similarly, there is substantial uncertainty regarding the estimation of the virial radius. The line width is assigned an uncertainty of 20%. Battersby et al. (2010) found the virial mass 68% confidence interval to be approximately 50% to 170% of the quoted value. Assigned uncertainties are detailed in Table 6.2 and 6.3.

Chapter 7

Conclusions

This study sought to shed light on the nature of star formation in the various parts of the CMZ and how different environmental factors play a role. The two clouds investigated in this study are in distinct locations and inhabit different environments. By applying consistent methods to each cloud, we hope to answer the greater question of the observed suppressed star formation in the CMZ. In addition, the results of the 1.6 Degree Cloud, allow the ability us to test our methods by comparing them with the results of Graham (2015).

The 1.6 Degree Cloud contains at least one star-forming core and is largely consistent with the results of Graham (2015). Although star formation is not expected as the cloud is suspected to be in a location of high turbulence, evidence of at least one star-forming core suggests a possibility for local, smaller-scale, star formation. This possibility can be investigated further using higher-resolution observations. Cores that the SMA Legacy Survey could not resolve may exist and would provide more evidence.

The 1.1 Degree Cloud also contains at least one core, though the star-forming nature of this core is uncertain. As a result of being plagued by numerous issues during the observation process, it is likely that further study of the 1.1 Degree Cloud will require further observation.

The procedure for imaging and feather the spectral line data remains a work in progress. As the signal-to-noise ratio is inherently lower in spectral line data, processing the data is

correspondingly more challenging. More work is required to determine the optimal method to process the data. Based on this study, the method used by Jens Kauffman is a computationally quicker procedure that generates reasonably good images that were used in this study. In comparison, Mark Graham's methods required more time in addition to requiring an interactive step. These seem to be beneficial as the results appear to be better in quality. Although, this study was not able to fully and in depth investigate and compare the two methods, it appears that the suitability of each method varies depending on situation.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Derivations

A.1 Virial Mass

Given a density profile of $\rho(r) = r^\beta$, the virial mass of a cloud can be given by:

$$M_{\text{vir}} = 3 \left[\frac{5 - 2\beta}{3 - \beta} \right] \frac{R\sigma^2}{G} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where β is the spectral index. For $\beta = 2$, this becomes:

$$M_{\text{vir}} = 3 \frac{R\sigma^2}{G} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Converting the gravitational constant into useful units:

$$G \approx \frac{1}{232} \frac{\text{pc km}^2 \text{ s}^{-2}}{M_\odot} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The full width at half maximum is given as $FWHM = 2a$. Here a is that standard deviation and is related to the velocity dispersion σ by:

$$\frac{1}{2} = e^{-\frac{a^2}{2\sigma^2}} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

This can be reduced by taking the natural log and then rearranging:

$$\sigma = \frac{\Delta v_{\text{FWHM}}}{2\sqrt{2 \ln 2}} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Combining everything:

$$M_{\text{vir}} = 126 \frac{R_{\text{vir}}}{1 \text{ pc}} \left(\frac{\Delta v_{\text{FWHM}}}{1 \text{ km s}^{-1}} \right)^2 M_{\odot} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

This derivation is adapted from Graham (2015).

Appendix B

IDL and Python Code

Appendix B contains code used to prepare and image as well as analyze data from the SMA, BGPS, and APEX. The imaging of each cloud involved a majority of the time spent on this study. It is included here for reference.

B.1 Preperation of Calibrated Data

B.1.1 IDL with MIR Package

```
; Restore your calibrated data
mir_restore, 'track23_final.mg.mir'

; Select all the data
select, /p, /re

; Compile mir2
.compile mir2.pro

;lower side band G1.602+0.018 [Compact only - for subcompact, replace .sc. with .sc.]
mir2, dir='G1.602.sc.lsb.if1', sideband='l', source='G1.602+0.018', band=['s01','s02','s03','s04','s05',
    's06','s07','s08','s09','s10','s11','s12','s13','s14','s15','s16','s17','s18','s19','s20','s21','s22',
    's23','s24']

mir2, dir='G1.602.sc.lsb.if2', sideband='l', source='G1.602+0.018', band=['s25','s26','s27','s28','s29',
    's30','s31','s32','s33','s34','s35','s36','s37','s38','s39','s40','s41','s42','s43','s44','s45','s46',
    's47','s48','s49'] // added s49, but not s50

; upper side band
mir2, dir='G1.602.sc.usb.if1', sideband='u', source='G1.602+0.018', band=['s01','s02','s03','s04','s05',
    's06','s07','s08','s09','s10','s11','s12','s13','s14','s15','s16','s17','s18','s19','s20','s21','s22
```

```

', 's23', 's24']

mir2, dir='G1.602.sc.usb.if2', sideband='u', source='G1.602+0.018', band=['s25', 's26', 's27', 's28', 's29',
's30', 's31', 's32', 's33', 's34', 's35', 's36', 's37', 's38', 's39', 's40', 's41', 's42', 's43', 's44', 's45', 's46',
's47', 's48', 's49']

```

B.2 Dust Continuum Imaging

B.2.1 MIRIAD Package

```

;# Visualise the visibility spectra to determine continuum channels
uvspec nxy=1,1 axis=chan,amp interval=9999 device=/ps options=avall,nobase vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1
uvspec nxy=1,1 axis=chan,amp interval=9999 device=/ps options=avall,nobase vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2
uvspec nxy=1,1 axis=chan,amp interval=9999 device=/ps options=avall,nobase vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if1
uvspec nxy=1,1 axis=chan,amp interval=9999 device=/ps options=avall,nobase vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if2

;# Separate the continuum from the spectral line data, dust from molecular lines, visually look to see
what the chans are
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1 out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0 mode=chan0 options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,400,600,1000,1100,1500,1600,2000,2100,2700,2800,3000,3072
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1 out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.line mode=line options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,400,600,1000,1100,1500,1600,2000,2100,2700,2800,3000,3072
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2 out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0 mode=chan0 options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,400,700,1000,1100,1300,1400,1500,1600,1900,2100,2500,2600
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2 out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.line mode=line options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,400,700,1000,1100,1300,1400,1500,1600,1900,2100,2500,2600
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if1 out=G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0 mode=chan0 options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,300,600,1000,1100,1400,1600,2000,2100,2700,2800,3000,3072
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if1 out=G1.602.sc.usb.if1.line mode=line options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,300,600,1000,1100,1400,1600,2000,2100,2700,2800,3000,3072
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if2 out=G1.602.sc.usb.if2.ch0 mode=chan0 options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,1000,1100,1300,1400,1500,1700,2500,2600,3000,3072
uvlin vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if2 out=G1.602.sc.usb.if2.line mode=line options=nocal,nopass,nopol,nowin order
=2 chans=1,100,1000,1100,1300,1400,1500,1700,2500,2600,3000,3072

;# Change the rest frequency {to reflect each line}{Just changing the header}
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.usb.if1.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=230.53800 out=G1.602.sc.12CO.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=220.39868 out=G1.602.sc.13CO.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=219.56036 out=G1.602.sc.C18O.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=217.10498 out=G1.602.sc.SiO.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=218.22219 out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.1.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=218.47563 out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.2.temp
uvputhd vis=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.line type=d hdvar=restfreq varval=218.76007 out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.3.temp

;# Regrid the channels between -200 and 200 km/s; From the feature/line
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.12CO.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.12CO
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.13CO.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.13CO
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.C18O.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.C18O
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.SiO.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.SiO
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO.1.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.1
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO.2.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.2
uvaver vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO.3.temp line='velocity,360,200,1.1,-1.1' out=G1.602.sc.H2CO.3

```

```

;# Look at the spread in velocity [Plots it and looks at it, Sanity check]
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.12CO interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.13CO interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.C18O interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.SiO interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO_1 interval=9999 device=/xw axis=freq,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO_2 interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1
smauvspec vis=G1.602.sc.H2CO_3 interval=9999 device=/xw axis=velo,amp options=avall,nobase,nopol nxy=1,1

;# Remove the temporary file
rm -rf G1.602.sc.12CO.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.13CO.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.C18O.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.SiO.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.H2CO_1.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.H2CO_2.temp
rm -rf G1.602.sc.H2CO_3.temp

;# Export the visibility data to uvfits (lines)
fits in=G1.602.sc.12CO op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.12CO.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.13CO op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.13CO.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.C18O op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.C18O.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.SiO op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.SiO.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.H2CO_1 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.H2CO_1.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.H2CO_2 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.H2CO_2.uvfits
fits in=G1.602.sc.H2CO_3 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.H2CO_3.uvfits

;# Export the visibility data to uvfits (dust continuums)
fits in=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0.fits
fits in=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0.fits
fits in=G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0.fits
fits in=G1.602.sc.usb.if2.ch0 op=uvout out=G1.602.sc.usb.if2.ch0.fits

```

B.2.2 CASA

```

# Import the uvfits files
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.c.lsb.if1.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.c.lsb.if1.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.c.lsb.if2.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.c.lsb.if2.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.c.usb.if1.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.c.usb.if1.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.c.usb.if2.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.c.usb.if2.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0.ms')
importuvfits(fitsfile='G1.602.sc.usb.if2.ch0.fits', vis='G1.602.sc.usb.if2.ch0.ms')

# Merge uvfits files
myfiles=['G1.602.c.lsb.if1.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.c.lsb.if2.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.c.usb.if1.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.c.usb.
        if2.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.sc.lsb.if1.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.sc.lsb.if2.ch0.ms', 'G1.602.sc.usb.if1.ch0.ms', 'G1
        .602.sc.usb.if2.ch0.ms']

# Merge all visibilities freqtol
concat(vis=myfiles, concatvis='G1.602.cont.V1.ms', timesort=True, freqtol='0.5GHz')

```

```

# Check the observation information and the visibility data
listobs(vis='G1.602.cont.V1.ms')
plotms(vis='G1.602.cont.V1.ms', xaxis='channel', yaxis='amplitude')

# To determine threshold for cleaning
# make a dirty image (niter=0)
# close and re-open the cube using the viewer
# select the box region tool
# for a continuum image, make a box near the edge of the field
# for a spectral cube, choose a line free channel
# double-click inside
# the rms noise inside the box will appear under Regions Statistics)
# try a few different boxes
# average the results to get ?
# the threshold should be at least 3?

# Make a dirty image
clean(vis='G1.602.cont.V1.ms', imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.2', uvrange='', field='', spw='', niter=0, gain
      =0.1, threshold='', psfmode='clark', imagermode='mosaic', scaletype='SAULT', ftmachine='mosaic',
      interactive=True, phasecenter='J2000_17h49m19_-27d33m24')
#J2000 17h49m19 -27d33m24
# Perform cleaning
clean(vis='G1.602.cont.V1.ms', imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1', uvrange='', field='', spw='', niter=10000,
      gain=0.1, threshold='12mJy', psfmode='clark', imagermode='mosaic', scaletype='SAULT', ftmachine='
      mosaic', interactive=True, npercycle=20, imsize=360, cell="1arcsec", minpb=0.1, pbcor=False,
      weighting='natural', stokes='I', chaniter=False, phasecenter='J2000_17h49m19_-27d33m24')

# Construct a primary beam corrected image from an image and a primary beam pattern
impbcor(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.image', pbimage='G1.602.cont.V1.1.flux', outfile='G1.602.cont.V1.1.
      pbcor')

# Export fits file
exportfits(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.image', fitsimage='G1.602.cont.V1.1.image.fits')

# Feather with BGPS data
# import fits
feather(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather', highres='G1.602.cont.V1.1.image', lowres='CMZ.ring_1.3
      mm_J2000.image')

# Export final fits file
exportfits(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather', fitsimage='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather.fits')

# Regrid to the Galactic plane
imregrid(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather', template='GALACTIC', output='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather.gal
      ')

# Export regridded fits file
exportfits(imagename='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather.gal', fitsimage='G1.602.cont.V1.1.feather.gal.fits')

```

B.3 Molecular Line

B.3.1 Method One

This method of combining single-dish molecular line data and interferometer molecular line data is used by Mark Graham in Graham (2015).

```
#
# set up parameters
#

# load some libraries
import re
import shutil
import os
from time import ctime

print '>>>_Script_started_at_' + ctime()

# set up some variables
LineID = 'H2CO_1'
RestFrequency = '218.2222GHz'      # must be in GHz
SidebandID = 'lsb'
SourceID = 'G1.602+0.018'
Source = 'G1.602'

SDImage = 'cutout_G1.63-0.02_217to219_b1.fits'
SourceLocation = 'J2000_17h49m19_-27d33m24'
ImageSize = [400, 400]
NumberIterations = 10000
CleaningThreshold = '200mJy'

VelocityResolution = '1.1km/s'     # must be in km/s
StartVelocity = '-200km/s'
NumberChannels = 360

CellSize = '1arcsec'

# copy uvfits file into imaging directory
Compact = '../..../' + SourceID + '/' + Source + '.c.' + LineID + '.uvfits'
Subcompact = '../..../' + SourceID + '/' + Source + '.sc.' + LineID + '.uvfits'
shutil.copy2(Compact, os.getcwd())
shutil.copy2(Subcompact, os.getcwd())

print '>>>_Copied_' + Source + '.c.' + LineID + '.uvfits' + '_and_' + Source + '.sc.' + LineID + '.uvfits'
      '_to_imaging_directory'

# import uvfits file into CASA
os.system('rm_-rf_c.' + LineID + '.ms')
os.system('rm_-rf_sc.' + LineID + '.ms')

importuvfits(fitsfile = Source + '.c.' + LineID + '.uvfits', vis='c.' + LineID + '.ms')
```

```

importuvfits(fitsfile = Source + '.sc.' + LineID + '.uvfits', vis='sc.' + LineID + '.ms')

print '>>_Imported_uvfits_files_into_CASA'

# merge uvfits files and export
os.system('rm -rf ' + LineID + '.ms')
os.path.exists(LineID + '.uvfits') and os.remove(LineID + '.uvfits')

myfiles=['c.' + LineID + '.ms', 'sc.' + LineID + '.ms']
concat(vis=myfiles, concatvis = LineID + '.ms', timesort=True, freqtol='0.5GHz')
exportuvfits(vis = LineID + '.ms', fitsfile = LineID + '.uvfits')

print '>>_Merged_CASA_files_and_exported_to_uvfits'

# make directories if non existent and move uvfits
uvfits='../data_uv/uv_fits/' + LineID
uvcasa='../data_uv/uv_casa/' + LineID

if not os.path.exists(uvfits): os.makedirs(uvfits)
if not os.path.exists(uvcasa): os.makedirs(uvcasa)

fitsfile = LineID + '.uvfits'
newfile = SourceID + '_' + SidebandID + '.uvfits'
folder = '../data_uv/uv_fits/' + LineID + '/'

if not os.path.exists(folder): os.makedirs(folder)

os.rename(fitsfile, newfile)
print '>>_Renamed_' + fitsfile + '_as_' + newfile

os.path.exists(folder + newfile) and os.remove(folder + newfile)

shutil.move(newfile, folder)

print '>>_Moved_' + newfile + '_to_' + folder

print ">>_Set-up_done,_let's_search_" + SourceID + '_for_' + LineID + '!'

# set some more variables

SizeSingleDishMeter = 12.
SDEfficiency = 0.75 # main beam efficiency to scale to Jansky
SDCutoffScaleMeter = 6. # UV cutoff scale for Feather

# some additional conversions
RestFrequencyGHz = float(RestFrequency.replace('GHz', ''))
VelocityResolutionKMS = float(VelocityResolution.replace('km/s', ''))
FrequencyResolution = str(333.564095*VelocityResolutionKMS*(RestFrequencyGHz/100.)) + 'kHz'
CellSizeArcsec = float(CellSize.replace('arcsec', ''))
SingleDishResolutionArcsec = 74.88 / (RestFrequencyGHz/100.) / \
    (SizeSingleDishMeter/10.)

#
# prepare visibilities
#

```

```

# ingest UVFITS file into CASA
UVFileNaming = LineID + '/' + SourceID + '_' + SidebandID
os.system('rm -rf ../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms')
importuvfits('../data_uv/uv_fits/' + UVFileNaming + '.uvfits', \
              vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms')

print '>>_Imported_SMA_data_into_CASA'

# create a simple dirty image
os.system('rm -rf_deconvolved*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved',
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'natural',
      niter = 0,
      threshold = '20mJy',
      usescratch = True)

print '>>_Made_dirty_image_of_SMA_data_-_"deconvolved.image"'

#
# prepare single-dish data
#

# convert APEX map
importfits(fitsimage = '../data_sd/' + SDImage,
          imagename='apex.image',
          overwrite=True)
imhead('apex.image',
      mode='put',
      hdkey='telescope', hdvalue='ALMA')
imhead('apex.image',
      mode='put',
      hdkey='restfreq', hdvalue=RestFrequency)

print '>>_Imported_APEX_data_-_"apex.image"'

# smooth the velocity axis of the APEX data
SDCellSizeX = str(abs(imhead('apex.image', mode='get', hdkey='cdelt1')['value'] * \
                          180.*3600./pi)) + 'arcsec'
SDCellSizeY = str(abs(imhead('apex.image', mode='get', hdkey='cdelt2')['value'] * \
                          180.*3600./pi)) + 'arcsec'

```

```

os.system('rm -rf apex_vsmooth.image')
ia.open('apex.image')
im2 = ia.sepconvolve(outfile='apex_vsmooth.image',
                    axes=[0,1,2], types=['box','box','box'],
                    widths=[SDCellSizeX,SDCellSizeY,FrequencyResolution],
                    overwrite=True)
im2.done()
ia.close()

print '>>>Smoothed the velocity axis of the APEX data ->' apex_vsmooth.image''

# beat the stokes axis into proper format
os.system('rm -rf apex_vsmooth.stokes.image')
ia.open('apex_vsmooth.image')
im2 = ia.regrid(dropdeg=True)
im3 = im2.adddegaxes(outfile='apex_vsmooth.stokes.image', overwrite=True,
                    stokes='I')
im2.done()
im3.done()
ia.close()

print '>>>Beaten Stokes axis into the proper format ->' apex_vsmooth.stokes.image''

imhead('apex_vsmooth.stokes.image')

os.system('rm -rf apex_trans.image')
imtrans(imagename='apex_vsmooth.stokes.image',
        outfile='apex_trans.image',
        order='0132')

print '>>>Reordered image axes ->' apex_trans.image''

# regrid single-dish image
os.system('rm -rf apex_trans_regrid.image')
ReferenceFrame = imregrid('deconvolved.image', template='get')
imregrid(imagename='apex_trans.image',
        template=ReferenceFrame,
        output='apex_trans_regrid.image',
        asvelocity=True,
        interpolation='linear',
        overwrite=True)

print '>>>Regridded the APEX data ->' apex_trans_regrid''

# flux conversion scaling for single-dish image
JyperKelvin = 0.817 * (RestFrequencyGHz/100.)**2. * \
              (SingleDishResolutionArcsec/10.)**2.
FactorJyperPixel = CellSizeArcsec**2. / \
                  (1.133 * SingleDishResolutionArcsec**2.)
ConversionFactor = JyperKelvin * FactorJyperPixel / SDEfficiency

os.system('rm -rf apex_trans_regrid_scaled.image')

```

```

im1 = ia.imagecalc(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled.image',
                   pixels=str(ConversionFactor)+'*apex_trans_regrid.image',
                   overwrite=True)

im1.done()
ia.close()

imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled.image',
       mode='put',
       hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='Jy/pixel')

print '>>>Scaled_brightness_unit_to_Jy/pixel--' apex_trans_regrid_scaled.image''

# correct single-dish image for the primary beam sensitivity
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image')
immath(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image',
       imagename=['deconvolved.flux',
                  'apex_trans_regrid_scaled.image'],
       mode='evalexpr', expr='IM0*IM1')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image',
       mode='put',
       hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='Jy/pixel')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image',
       mode='put',
       hdkey='bmaj', hdvalue=str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+'arcsec')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image',
       mode='put',
       hdkey='bmin', hdvalue=str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+'arcsec')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image',
       mode='put',
       hdkey='bpa', hdvalue='0deg')

print '>>>Corrected_APEX_data_for_the_primary_beam_sensitivity--' apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image''

# remove blanking for single-dish data
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image')
os.system('cp-r_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor.image_ +
          'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image')
ia.open('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image')
ia.replacemaskedpixels(0., update=True)
ia.close()

print '>>>Removed_the_masked_pixels_and_set_to_0--' apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image''

# remove negative values in single-dish image
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked_nonneg.image')
immath(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked_nonneg.image',
       imagename=['apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image'],
       mode='evalexpr', expr='iif(IM0>=-0.00,IM0,-0.0)')

print '>>>Removed_negative_values_from_APEX_data--' apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked_nonneg.image''

#

```

```

# do the deconvolution via CLEAN
#

# do a coarse cleaning
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      modelimage = 'apex-trans-regrid-scaled-pbcor-unmasked-noneg.image',
      imagename = 'deconvolved-sdinput',
      multiscale = [0,5,10,15,20],
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'natural',
      niter = 10,
      cyclefactor = 5.,
      threshold = CleaningThreshold,
      usescratch = True)

print '>>_Done_initial_coarse_cleaning,_non-interactive_-'deconvolved-sdinput''

# remove negative intensities in model
os.system('mv_deconvolved-sdinput.model_deconvolved-sdinput-orig.model')
immath(outfile='deconvolved-sdinput.model',
      imagename=['deconvolved-sdinput-orig.model'],
      mode='evalexpr',expr='iif(IM0_>=0.00,IM0,_0.0)')

print '>>_Removed_negative_values_in_model_-'deconvolved-sdinput.model''

# continue with finer cleaning
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved-sdinput',
      multiscale = [0,5,10,15,20],
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = True, # can we make this false
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'natural',

```

```

        niter = NumberIterations,
        cyclefactor = 5.,
        threshold = CleaningThreshold,
        usescratch = True)

print '>>>Continue_with_finer_cleaning,_interactive_--"deconvolved-sdinput"'

# unmask interferometer data for feathering
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
os.system('cp-r_deconvolved-sdinput.image_deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
ia.open('deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
ia.replacemaskedpixels(0., update=True)
ia.close()

print '>>>Removed_the_masked_pixels_and_set_to_0_--"deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image"'

#
# do the deconvolution via CLEAN
#

# do a coarse cleaning
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      modelimage = 'apex-trans-regrid-scaled-pbcor-unmasked-noneg.image',
      imagename = 'deconvolved-sdinput',
      multiscale = [0,5,10,15,20],
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'natural',
      niter = 10,
      cyclefactor = 5.,
      threshold = CleaningThreshold,
      usescratch = True)

print '>>>Done_initial_coarse_cleaning,_non-interactive_--"deconvolved-sdinput"'

# remove negative intensities in model
os.system('mv_deconvolved-sdinput.model_deconvolved-sdinput-orig.model')
immath(outfile='deconvolved-sdinput.model',
      imagename=['deconvolved-sdinput-orig.model'],
      mode='evalexpr',expr='iif(IM0_>=0.00,IM0,-0.0)')

print '>>>Removed_negative_values_in_model_--"deconvolved-sdinput.model"'

```

```

# continue with finer cleaning
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved-sdinput',
      multiscale = [0,5,10,15,20],
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = True, # false?
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'natural',
      niter = NumberIterations,
      cyclefactor = 5.,
      threshold = CleaningThreshold,
      usescratch = True)

print '>>>Continue_with_finer_cleaning,_interactive_--"deconvolved-sdinput"'

# unmask interferometer data for feathering
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
os.system('cp-r_deconvolved-sdinput.image_deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
ia.open('deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image')
ia.replacemaskedpixels(0., update=True)
ia.close()

print '>>>Removed_the_masked_pixels_and_set_to_0_--"deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image"'

#
# feather the data
#

# feather the data
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-combi.image')
feather(imagename = 'deconvolved-combi.image',
      highres = 'deconvolved-sdinput-unmasked.image',
      lowres = 'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_pbcor_unmasked.image',
      effdishdiam = SDCutoffScaleMeter,
      lowpassfiltersd = True)

print '>>>Feathered_the_data_--"deconvolved-combi.image"'

# correct feathered image for primary beam scaling
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-combi-pbcor.image')
immath(outfile='deconvolved-combi-pbcor.image',
      imagename=['deconvolved-combi.image',
                 'deconvolved-sdinput.flux'],
      mode='evalexpr',expr='IM0/IM1')

```

```

ia.open('deconvolved-combi-pbcor.image')
ia.replacemaskedpixels(0., update=True)
ia.close()

print '>>>Corrected_f Feathered_image_for_primary_beam_scaling' deconvolved-combi-pbcor.image''

#
# steps below only serve checking the data
#

# smooth the resulting image to the single-dish beam
os.system('rm-rf deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo.image')
imsmooth(imagename = 'deconvolved-combi-pbcor.image',
         outfile = 'deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo.image',
         kernel = 'gauss',
         major = str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+' arcsec',
         minor = str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+' arcsec',
         pa = '0deg',
         targetres = True)

print '>>>Smoothed_the_resulting_image_to_the_single-dish_beam' deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo.image''

# convert the smoothed image back to the Kelvin scale
os.system('rm-rf deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo-Kelvin.image')
immath(outfile='deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo-Kelvin.image',
       imagename=['deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo.image'],
       mode='evalexpr', expr='IM0/'+str(JyperKelvin))
imhead('deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo-Kelvin.image',
      mode='put',
      hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='K')

print '>>>Converted_the_smoothed_image_back_to_the_Kelvin_scale' deconvolved-combi-pbcor-smo-Kelvin.
image''

# if not os.path.exists('/data/dlee/' + Source + '/' + LineID):
#     os.makedirs('/data/dlee/' + Source + '/' + LineID)

print '>>>All_done!'

print ">>>Don't forget to copy the output files to the new location otherwise they will be wiped the
next time you run this code!"

# print '>>> New location: /data/dlee/' + Source + '/' + LineID

print '>>>Script_finished_at' + ctime()

```

B.3.2 Method Two

This method of combining single-dish molecular line data and interferometer molecular line data is provided by Jens Kauffmann from the Max Planck Institute for Radio Astronomy.

This method was used to produce the combined SMA and APEX data analyzed in this study.

```

#
# Jens Kauffmann, jens.kauffmann@gmail.com
#
# 2015 July 27
#
# execfile('test_modelimage.py')

# load some libraries
import re
from time import ctime

print '>>_Script_started_at_' + ctime()

# provide line information
LineID = 'H2CO_1'
RestFrequency = '218.2222GHz'      # must be in GHz
SidebandID = 'lsb'

# provide source information
SourceID = 'G1.602+0.018' #good
SDImage = 'cutout_G1.63-0.02_217to219_b1.fits' #good
SourceLocation = 'J2000_17h49m19_-27d33m24' #good
ImageSize = [400, 400] #good ?
NumberIterations = 10000
CleaningThreshold = '100mJy'
StartVelocity = '-200km/s'
NumberChannels = 360
FudgeScale = 1.      # adjustment for flux calibration errors

# target resolution
VelocityResolution = '1.1km/s'      # must be in km/s
CellSize = '1arcsec'

# information on single-dish telescope
SizeSingleDishMeter = 12.
SDEfficiency = 0.75      # main beam efficiency to scale to Jansky
SDCutoffScaleMeter = 8.      # UV cutoff scale for feathering

# some additional conversions
RestFrequencyGHz = float(RestFrequency.replace('GHz', ''))
VelocityResolutionKMS = float(VelocityResolution.replace('km/s', ''))
FrequencyResolution = str(333.564095*VelocityResolutionKMS*(RestFrequencyGHz/100.)) + 'kHz'
CellSizeArcsec = float(CellSize.replace('arcsec', ''))
SingleDishResolutionArcsec = 74.88 / (RestFrequencyGHz/100.) / \
    (SizeSingleDishMeter/10.)

#
# prepare visibilities
#

# ingest UVFITS file into CASA
UVFileNaming = LineID + '/' + SourceID + '_' + SidebandID
print '>>_Importing_UV_' + UVFileNaming + '.uvfits_as_' + UVFileNaming + '.ms'

```

```

os.system('rm-rf../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms')
importuvfits('../data_uv/uv_fits/' + UVFileNaming + '.uvfits', \
              vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms')

# create a single channel dirty image
print '>>>_Creating_single_channel_dirty_image'
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved',
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'briggs',
      niter = 0,
      threshold = '20mJy',
      usescratch = True)

imhead('deconvolved.image')
print '>>>_Created_deconvolved_image'

#
# prepare single-dish data
#

# convert APEX map
print '>>>_Importing_single_dish_data_from../data_sd' + SDImage 'as_apex.image'
importfits(fitsimage = '../data_sd/' + SDImage,
           imagename='apex.image',
           overwrite=True)
imhead('apex.image',
      mode='put',
      hdkey='telescope', hdvalue='ALMA')

# smooth the velocity axis of the APEX data
print '>>>_Smoothing_velocity_axis_of_APEX_data'
SDCellSizeX = str(abs(imhead('apex.image', mode='get', hdkey='cdelt1')['value'] * \
                       180.*3600./pi)) + 'arcsec'
SDCellSizeY = str(abs(imhead('apex.image', mode='get', hdkey='cdelt2')['value'] * \
                       180.*3600./pi)) + 'arcsec'
os.system('rm-rf_apex_vsmooth.image')
ia.open('apex.image')
im2 = ia.sepconvolve(outfile='apex_vsmooth.image',
                    axes=[0,1,2], types=['box', 'box', 'box'],
                    widths=[SDCellSizeX, SDCellSizeY, FrequencyResolution],
                    overwrite=True)

```

```

im2.done()
ia.close()

# beat the stokes axis into proper format
print '>>_Making_stokes_axis_into_proper_format'
os.system('rm-rf_apex_vsmooth_stokes_image')
ia.open('apex_vsmooth_image')
im2 = ia.regrid(dropdeg=True)
im3 = im2.adddegaxes(outfile='apex_vsmooth_stokes_image', overwrite=True,
                    stokes='I')

im2.done()
im3.done()
ia.close()

imhead('apex_vsmooth_stokes_image')

os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_image')
imtrans(imagename='apex_vsmooth_stokes_image',
        outfile='apex_trans_image',
        order='0132')

imhead('apex_trans_image')

# regrid single-dish image
print '>>_Regridding_single-dish_image'
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_image')
ReferenceFrame = imregrid('deconvolved_image', template='get')
imregrid(imagename='apex_trans_image',
        template=ReferenceFrame,
        output='apex_trans_regrid_image',
        asvelocity=True,
        interpolation='linear',
        overwrite=True)

imhead('apex_trans_regrid_image')
imhead('deconvolved_image')

# flux conversion scaling for single-dish image
print '>>_Flux_conversion_scaling_for_single-dish_image'
JyperKelvin = 0.817 * (RestFrequencyGHz/100.)**2. * \
              (SingleDishResolutionArcsec/10.)**2.
FactorJyperPixel = CellSizeArcsec**2. / \
                  (1.133 * SingleDishResolutionArcsec**2.)
ConversionFactor = FudgeScale * JyperKelvin * FactorJyperPixel / SDEfficiency

os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_image')
im1 = ia.imagecalc(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled_image',
                  pixels=str(ConversionFactor)+'*apex_trans_regrid_image',
                  overwrite=True)

im1.done()
ia.close()

imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_image',

```

```

mode='put',
hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='Jy/pixel')

# remove blanking for single-dish data
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_image')
os.system('cp-r_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_image_' +
          'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_image')
ia.open('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_image')
ia.replacemaskedpixels(0., update=True)
ia.close()

# remove negative values in single-dish image
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_noneg_image')
immath(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_noneg_image',
        imagename=['apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_image'],
        mode='evalexpr', expr='iif(IM0 >= -0.00, _IM0, -0.0)')

#
# produce a first model of combined interferometer and SD data
#
print '>>>_Make_first_model_of_combined_SD_and_SMA_data.'
# clean the UV data
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved_sinput*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv_casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved_sinput',
      modelimage = 'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_noneg_image',
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'briggs',
      niter = NumberIterations,
      cyclefactor = 5.,
      threshold = CleaningThreshold,
      usescratch = True)

# get the positive interferometer-only clean components
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved_sinput_intmodel')
immath(outfile='deconvolved_sinput_intmodel',
        imagename=['deconvolved_sinput_model',
                  'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_noneg_image'],
        mode='evalexpr',
        expr='iif((IM0-IM1) >= -0.00, _IM0-IM1, -0.0)')

```

```

# remove those components if they are at the map edge
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput-masked.intmodel')
immath(outfile='deconvolved-sdinput-masked.intmodel',
        imagename=['deconvolved-sdinput.intmodel',
                   'deconvolved-sdinput.flux.pbcoverage'],
        mode='valexpr',
        expr='if((IM1)_>=_0.25, _IM0, _0.0)')

imhead('deconvolved-sdinput-masked.intmodel',
        mode='put',
        hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='Jy/pixel')

# smooth the interferometer-only components to the synthesized beam
SynthBeamMaj = imhead('deconvolved-sdinput.image', mode='get', hdkey='bmaj')['value']
SynthBeamMin = imhead('deconvolved-sdinput.image', mode='get', hdkey='bmin')['value']
SynthBeamPA = imhead('deconvolved-sdinput.image', mode='get', hdkey='bpa')['value']

os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-sdinput.intimage')
imsmooth(imagename='deconvolved-sdinput-masked.intmodel',
         outfile='deconvolved-sdinput.intimage',
         kernel='gauss',
         major=str(SynthBeamMaj)+' arcsec',
         minor=str(SynthBeamMin)+' arcsec',
         pa=str(SynthBeamPA)+' deg')

# produce a non-negative single-dish map in Jy/beam
os.system('rm-rf_apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image')
immath(outfile='apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        imagename=['apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg.image'],
        mode='valexpr', expr='IM0/' + str(FactorJyperPixel))

imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        mode='put',
        hdkey='bunit', hdvalue='Jy/beam')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        mode='put',
        hdkey='bmaj', hdvalue=str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+' arcsec')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        mode='put',
        hdkey='bmin', hdvalue=str(SingleDishResolutionArcsec)+' arcsec')
imhead('apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        mode='put',
        hdkey='bpa', hdvalue='0deg')

# feather the data
os.system('rm-rf_deconvolved-combi.model')
feather(imagename = 'deconvolved-combi.model',
        highres = 'deconvolved-sdinput.intimage',
        lowres = 'apex_trans_regrid_scaled_unmasked_nonneg_perbeam.image',
        effdishdiam = SDCutoffScaleMeter,
        lowpassfiltersd = True)

```

```

# clean up and keep the final model
os.system('rm_rf_combimodel.image')
os.system('mv_deconvolved-combi.model_combimodel.image')

#
# second and final cleaning with new model
#
print '>>_Make_second/final_model_of_combined_SD_and_SMA_data.'

# clean the UV data
os.system('rm_rf_deconvolved-sdinput*')
clean(vis = '../data_uv/uv.casa/' + UVFileNaming + '.ms',
      imagename = 'deconvolved-sdinput',
      modelimage = 'combimodel.image',
      spw='',
      restfreq = RestFrequency,
      imagermode = 'mosaic',
      mode = 'velocity',
      outframe='lsrk',
      width = VelocityResolution,
      start = StartVelocity,
      nchan = NumberChannels,
      interactive = False,
      imsize = ImageSize,
      cell = CellSize,
      phasecenter = SourceLocation,
      weighting = 'briggs',
      niter = NumberIterations,
      cyclefactor = 5.,
      threshold = CleaningThreshold,
      usescratch = True)

# viewer('deconvolved-sdinput.image')

print '>>_Created_final_file:_deconvolved-sdinput.image'
print '>>_Script_finished_at_' + ctime()

```